

AGROPHYSICAL AND AGROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAY-MEADOW SOILS IN BOYOVUT DISTRICT, SIRDARYO REGION

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of research conducted on the study of agrophysical and agrochemical properties of gray-grassland soils with varying degrees of salinity caused by anthropogenic factors at two observation sites with a total area of 57 hectares in the Bayavud district of the Syrdarya region, Galaba (21 ha) and Navbahor (36 ha), which show that it is necessary to establish effective use of bioameliorants to improve the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soil in order to prevent secondary salinization occurring during the season and create favorable conditions for agricultural crops.*

Keywords: *salinity, agrophysical properties, agrochemical properties, bioameliorant, agrotechnical measures.*

Introduction

In recent years, worldwide scientific research has been conducted on priority areas for increasing the fertility of irrigated soils through modern agrotechnologies. In the Decree PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, “On the Strategy for the Development of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026” of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, necessary strategic tasks aimed at “improving and preserving soil fertility” were outlined. Therefore, modern agrotechnologies are of particular importance for determining the effect of biomeliorants on the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of irrigated soils, their fertility, and the growth, development, and productivity of agricultural crops.

It is well known that in irrigated areas, efficient and rational use of land and water resources, restoration and preservation of soil fertility, and consistent increases in crop yields are among the most pressing contemporary issues. Therefore, it is necessary to implement various agrotechnical and meliorative measures correctly and in a timely manner, to monitor soil properties and its meliorative-ecological condition in detail, and to develop scientifically grounded recommendations based on the collected data [1,3].

Rational use of land resources in agriculture is of great importance, as it is related to increasing yields from irrigated lands and improving their economic efficiency. Restoration, preservation, and enhancement of soil fertility are among the most important tasks we face. Based on the results of research conducted by O. Toshbekov, I. Abdurakhmanov, and others, it can be noted that one of the low-cost methods to reduce soil salinization or prevent secondary salinization is the use of plant resources. In this context, the drought resistance of halophytes, their ability to produce high biomass with nutritional and medicinal properties in saline soils, and their suitability for use in soils with various degrees of salinity and poor agrophysical and agrochemical indicators are particularly important [3,4].

According to E.B. Dedov, phytomelioration of saline soils requires considering the relationship of plants to their environment, their meliorative effect on soil, and their potential use

in agriculture when selecting various life forms of plants (trees, shrubs, perennial grasses) and ecologically specialized crops such as xerophytes, halophytes, halo-xerophytes, mesophytes, hygrophytes, and phreatophytes [2].

Among such plants, licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) is the most valuable pharmacological raw material. Using licorice as a phytomeliorant has shown its effectiveness in improving the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of soils and increasing the efficiency of irrigation water use. Based on the above information, the aim of this study is to determine the effects of licorice as a biomesoliorant on the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of irrigated gray-desert soils with various levels of salinity, and to define agromeliorative measures necessary for enhancing the growth, development, and yield of cultivated crops.

The research was conducted during 2020–2023 in irrigated gray-desert soils with varying degrees of salinity in Boyovut District, Sirdaryo Region, at selected experimental sites (Galaba and Navbahor SIUs). In this area, the content of water-soluble salts in the arable layer and subsoil of gray-desert soils ranges from 0.3–0.9%, and the groundwater level fluctuates around 1.5–2.6 m.

One of the key parameters for increasing the biological productivity of degraded soils is the rapid growth of aboveground and underground plant biomass, which leads to the accumulation of organic residues in the soil. This also improves soil microbiological indicators [5–7]. In our experiments, by the third year of licorice growth, an increase in both aboveground and underground biomass and rapid root system development were observed. These indicators vary depending on the planting period and the level of soil salinity (Tables 1, 2, 3).

Table 1

Effect of planting periods on the formation of aboveground and underground wet biomass of licorice

Planting period	Date of sowing	Stem			Root		
		Weight of 1 stem		Kg\ ga.	Weight of 1 root		Kg\ ga
		Average	Difference		Average	Difference	
Autumn	25-X1 2019	167	77-215	170 67	510	200-852	193 25
Early spring	15-11- 2020	135	63-197	163 20	481	165-660	175 56

Table 2

The effect of soil salinity levels on the growth and development of the above-ground organs of licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*)

Salinity level	Stem				Lateral branches	
	Amount		Length ,sm		1 st type	
	Amount, number					
	Average	Difference	Average	Difference	Average	Difference
At the end of the first year of the growing season						
Low	1,0	1-1	69,4	51-80	24,4	17-28
	1,3	1-2	84,6	55-102	25,3	14-34
Medium	1,0	1-1	48,7	28-65	22,0	17-29
	1,2	1-2	57,6	41-74	23,1	19-30
At the end of the 3 rd year of the growing season						

Low	2,6	2-4	117,4	110-140	29,2	22-39
	3,2	2-6	171,8	141-183	26,2	24-31
Medium	2,4	1-5	88,0	70-89	28,0	22-34
	2,2	2-3	91,2	67-95	27,4	24-35

Table 3

Effect of soil salinity level on the fresh root mass of licorice plants

Salinity level	Seedling density at the end of the growing season, pcs/ha	Root mass			
		One root mass,gr		Kg\ ga	
		Average	Difference		
Medium	25380	397	220-540	10076	
	40572	650	290-1100	26372	
High	12429	257	200-370	3194	
	25454	321	160-670	8171	

The licorice plant (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) promotes the accumulation of organic matter in soil layers due to the rapid growth of its root system. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soil.

In fields planted with licorice, it was observed that the fertility level of the top one meter of soil increased, which subsequently improved the overall physical properties of the soil. The results indicate that in fields with weakly and moderately saline soils, from the third year after planting licorice, the physical properties of the soil in areas where plant roots spread improved. Specifically, soil compaction decreased, and the total porosity was maintained in a condition favorable for plant growth (Tables 4–5).

It is known that in fields planted with cotton and cereals, soil compaction in the top layers sharply increases by autumn, and total porosity decreases. Based on these observations, it can be concluded that licorice positively influences the optimization of soil agrophysical properties.

Table 4

Dynamics of agrophysical indicators of soils planted with licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) (Boyovut District, "Galaba SIU")

Layer depth, cm	Soil solid fraction density, g/cm ³		Soil bulk density, g/cm ³		Total porosity, %	
	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023
0-28	2,76	2,72	1,45	1,36	48,0	50,0
28-46	2,76	2,72	1,47	1,37	47,0	50,0
46-92	2,77	2,73	1,43	1,37	49,0	50,0
92-144	2,77	2,74	1,44	1,40	48,0	49,0
144-178	2,77	2,74	1,44	1,42	48,0	48,0
178-205	2,77	2,75	1,44	1,42	48,0	48,0

Table 5

Dynamics of agro-physical indicators of soils in fields planted with licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) (Boyovut District, "Navbahor SIU")

Layer depth, cm	Soil solid particle density, g/cm ³		Soil bulk density, g/cm ³		Total soil porosity, %	
	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023

0-28	2,76	2,72	1,44	1,34	48	51
28-46	2,76	2,72	1,46	1,36	47	50
46-92	2,77	2,73	1,42	1,38	49	50
92-144	2,77	2,74	1,42	1,39	49	49
144-178	2,77	2,74	1,42	1,40	49	49

Thus, during the study, in the third year in fields planted with licorice, soil density decreased compared to the initial year by 0.10 g/cm³ in the 0–28 cm layer and by an average of 0.04 g/cm³ in the layer up to one meter. Correspondingly, the total soil porosity increased by 2–3% (Tables 4–5).

Analyzing the agrochemical indicators of the experimental field soils, by autumn 2023, in areas where the plant roots had spread, an increase in humus and nitrogen content was observed, while the mobile phosphorus and potassium content slightly decreased (Tables 6–7).

Table 6

Agrochemical indicators of soils in fields planted with licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) (Boyovut District, “Galaba SIU”)

Layer depth, cm	Content of nutrient elements							
	Humus content, %		N, mg/kg		P ₂ O ₅ , mg/kg		K ₂ O, mg/kg	
	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023
0-15	0,95	1,02	37	48	17,2	16,0	144	127
15-50	0,85	0,90	35	42	18,6	15,4	138	122
50-100	0,52	0,64	28	32	10,8	9,87	115	110

Table 7

Agrochemical indicators of soils in fields planted with licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) (Boyovut district, Navbahor SIU) 2020

Layer depth, cm	Content of nutrient elements							
	Humus content, %		N, mg/kg		P ₂ O ₅ , mg/kg		K ₂ O, mg/kg	
	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023
0-15	0,87	1,12	28	44	18,4	15,3	128	117
15-50	0,75	0,99	32	43	16,6	14,4	118	102
50-100	0,46	0,54	21	25	11,8	10,5	120	108

Conclusion

Based on the above information, it can be concluded that the licorice plant (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), by producing a large amount of aboveground and underground biomass, has a positive effect on the agro-physical and agrochemical properties of slightly and moderately saline gray-meadow soils, demonstrating its phytomeliorative significance. Therefore, we recommend the use of licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) as a phytomeliorant to improve the agromeliorative condition of irrigated soils with varying degrees of salinity and to increase both the yield and quality of crops.

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